

Practices

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Demolitions and

Deconstructions

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#05 Demolitions and Deconstructions
Urszula Kozminska (Arkitektskolen Aarhus), Bie
Plevoets (UHasselt, As Found Network)

Demolitions and Deconstructions

The *Practices in Research* journal is an initiative of *Architecture In Practice*, an interuniversity research group of practising architects engaging their practice(s) at the heart of their research. In Practice explores the multiple ways in which architects can engage their professional architecture practice in academic research and reciprocally. “Practices in Research” (PiR) is an online journal for practice-based research in architecture and related disciplines, based on a selection of contributions to a conference. PiR explores the ways in which these practices engage or relate to research.

For PiR, the practice is not reduced to an illustration of theory. Inversely, the research is not reduced to the observation of practice. It aims at contributions in which research and practice mean mutual enrichment. PiR aims at research in which the practice is essential as a subject, a modality, a perspective and combinations thereof. The contributions are expected to stay in close contact with the practice, but they are not limited to the presentation or documentation of a practice. The contributions take a step beyond the reality of the practice in the way they present, explore, reveal a reflection in the field of architecture.

PiR also searches for creative forms of communication, questioning the usual hierarchy between text and image.

For PiR, visual and written narrations relate to each other in multiple ways. Images are more than illustrations, and text is more than an explanation.

This issue, *Demolitions and Deconstructions*, is based on a call for contributions that was published in January 2024. The call was composed with the essential support of Juliane Greb (UAntwerpen and büro Juliane Greb) and Benoît Burquel (ULB and AgwA). The following paragraphs were part of the initial open call.

“Moving towards a more ecological and sustainable building culture, many architects commit themselves to caring and maintaining our existing building stock. To reduce the consumption of resources, the production of waste and emissions, the aim is to first look at what is already there, before adding any new constructions.

At the same time, our built environment is a manifestation of social ideas, hierarchies, norms, and standards which often do not match the values, priorities, and expectations of today’s society. Lifestyles have diversified, family structures have evolved, modes of transportation have changed. Our buildings are based on anachronistic spatial patterns.

How do architects deal with this ambiguity? How do they decide on what can stay and what must go? When does demolition become unavoidable as a part of critical repair? How do architects negotiate between existing qualities and contemporary norms and expectations?

Partial demolitions often involve a series of artefacts: supporting structures, technical adaptations, material juxtapositions. They create a language as much as they question the nature of the project itself. Indeed, they cannot be reduced to operations based on patrimonial or technical considerations. Demolitions and deconstructions are deliberate choices, they are decisive in the design process, in its economy. They influence both the materiality and the spatiality of the project. Beyond a pragmatic approach to what is already there, how do partial demolition and supporting elements change the nature, the ambitions, the process, and the authorship of the project? And how does it then radically change the use of space afterwards?

What methods and processes do architects use when approaching an existing structure? How do they carefully and critically examine an existing building and how do they reveal its potential? What knowledge do they gain in the process of assessing what can stay and what must go? And finally, how can they afford to do so, given that architects' fees are still generally tied to construction costs, i.e., material and energy consumption?

Does the status of a caring architectural practice diverge from its ecological and social importance, as it does for many other caring professions?"

The Editorial Board was skillfully supported by Bie Plevoets (UHasselt, founder of the As Found network) and Urszula Kozminska (Arkitektskolen Aarhus), who acted as Editorial

Advisors. They were instrumental in filtering proposals, seeking contributions that thoughtfully addressed questions of careful yet experimental transformations. Submissions were expected to report on critical practices examining these questions while remaining grounded in their documentation and outcomes.

A preliminary selection of authors was invited to present at the Practice in Research conference at C.I.II.III.IV.A on May 27, 2024. Extended abstracts from the conference were published online in unreviewed proceedings. Following the event, a refined selection of contributors underwent a rigorous double-blind peer-review process for inclusion in this issue.

All contributions in this issue were thoroughly reviewed by two anonymous reviewers, adhering to the journal's established review policy. This issue also introduces a new format designed to challenge the conventional dominance of text over visual content. The format—a visual essay—limits submissions to 10 pages, including a brief introductory text (max. 150 words) and extended captions (max. 50 words per page), alongside a title page. These visual essays successfully underwent the same rigorous peer-review process, offering a balanced alternative to traditional articles.

Given the substantial increase in submissions, this issue is organized into thematic chapters that loosely mirror the conference structure. *Policies and Attitudes* explores methods for structuring and quantifying circular design

approaches from designers' perspectives. *Details of Demolitions* examines diverse architectural languages rooted in circularity and the role of deconstruction within projects. *Tactics of Demolitions* highlights how circularity influences architectural processes, often blurring lines between observation, design, and realization. *Structures and Constructions* reflects on the role of significant structural and constructive elements in transformation contexts. Finally, *Re-Presentations* offers experimental approaches to visual tools in circular design processes, diverging from traditional drawings, models, or renders for new constructions. This last chapter opens the door to potential future investigations, possibly forming the focal point of an upcoming issue.

To conclude this issue, the Editorial Board invited Bie Plevoets and Urszula Kozminska to co-author an overarching article reflecting on the initiative's setup and contributions. Their article provides a thoughtful synthesis of the coherence and diversity of *Demolitions and Deconstructions*. While not peer-reviewed, it complements the intentions of the Editorial Board and the institutions represented.

This issue also marked a milestone for the journal's organizational structure. Following the impulsion of the historical editors Benoît Burquel (ULB, AgwA), Harold Fallon (KU Leuven, AgwA) and Benoît Vandenbulcke (ULiège, AgwA), *Practices in Research* now operates with a wide and balanced Editorial Board, comprising representatives from the five universities supporting the *Architecture In Practice* research platform. Together with the Editor-in-Chief and

Associate Editor, the Editorial Board provides a dynamic yet stable framework, ensuring continuity and coherence. The Scientific Committee has also been restructured to strengthen connections across a broader academic and practice-based network.

Heartfelt thanks are extended to all contributors, advisors, reviewers, and members of the Editorial Board and Scientific Committee. Their collaboration has significantly expanded and deepened the journal's reflective scope, fostering meaningful discourse on ongoing architectural practices.

Harold Fallon, Benoit Burquel, Benoit Vandebulcke
Editor in Chief and Associate Editors.

